

Statistics of Afterpulses in Silicon Single-photon Detectors under Strong Pulsed Illumination

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Afterpulse statistics were experimentally studied for a number of single-photon detectors based on silicon avalanche photodiodes under intense illumination with nanosecond pulses. A significant increase in the probability of afterpulse occurrence was demonstrated for a large number of photons absorbed by the detectors. These results may be important for optimizing detector performance in quantum cryptography and for artificial pulsed neurons based on vertical-cavity lasers and single-photon avalanche photodiodes, one of whose operating modes is based on the action of sufficiently intense laser pulses.

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1. Introduction

Single-photon detectors are devices capable of detecting radiation at the level of individual photons. Their unique sensitivity allows them to operate at extremely low radiation intensities, making them indispensable in modern scientific research and high-tech applications [1]. Currently, there are several main types of detectors: avalanche photodiode detectors, photomultiplier tubes, superconducting material detectors, and silicon photomultiplier tubes. Single-photon detectors based on avalanche photodiodes have become widespread due to their high temporal resolution (less than 50 ps) [2, 3], their integration into CMOS structures, enabling the creation of compact detector arrays and matrices [4], and their compatibility with standard electronic components, simplifying the development of end devices.

A single-photon avalanche photodiode was shown to be a key element of an artificial spiking neuron (ASN), formed by a vertical-cavity surface-emitting laser (VCSEL) and a single-photon avalanche diode (SPAD) [5]. Such a neuron

can operate in two distinct modes: probabilistic or deterministic which depend on the amplitude of the incident laser pulses. In the deterministic mode, strong laser pulses are required, which under certain conditions can cause the average frequency of the neuron's output pulses to exceed the repetition rate of the input excitation pulses. This phenomenon is due to the effect of afterpulses, affecting photon counting statistics.

Afterpulsing in single-photon detectors is an important effect that needs to be considered in high-precision measurements. They consist of false triggering of the detector caused not by a photon's arrival, but by residual charge carriers. The cause is charge carrier trapping by impurity levels in the semiconductor structure. These charges stay at these levels for some time and, once released, can cause a repeated avalanche, without a new photon present. To characterize this phenomenon in single-photon detectors, afterpulse probability and the probability density distribution of afterpulses over time are used. Factors influencing afterpulse probability include temperature, voltage applied to the photodiode, and dead time.

Several main models have been proposed to describe afterpulse behavior, such as the single-exponential probability density model [6, 7],

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power model of the temporal dependence of the afterpulse distribution function [8], multiexponential afterpulse model with discrete energy distribution of traps (impurity levels) [9], and a model based on the assumption of impurity levels distributed as a zone rather than separate discrete levels [10]. As noted in [11], none of these models is universal, likely due to technological peculiarities of avalanche photodiode production. To mitigate the effects of afterpulses, common suppression techniques include optimizing the semiconductor structure to reduce impurity levels [12], applying digital signal processing algorithms to filter false triggers [13, 14], introducing additional corrective electronics [15], and increasing the detector's dead time [16], though the latter approach comes at the cost of reduced device speed.

The impact of avalanche photodiode afterpulses is especially critical in several fields, such as second-order autocorrelation measurements, where false events can skew the estimation of quantum entanglement degree or photon statistics. In quantum cryptography, afterpulses increase noise level, reducing reliability and security of key transmission [17–20]. This problem is also important in super-resolution fluorescence microscopy, where false events lead to artifacts during image reconstruction [21].

The goal of this work is to study the afterpulse statistics in single-photon detectors under high levels of pulsed laser excitation. As mentioned above, this interest is motivated by the use of SPADs as key elements of ASNs, one operating mode of which involves the use of short VCSEL pulses of relatively high intensity.

2. Experiment

The schematic of the experimental setup is presented in Figure 1(a). In the experiment, we used an ASN consisting of a thermostabilized VCSEL generating at 850 nm wavelength, an optical attenuator (consisting of fixed attenuators and a variable attenuator V800A (Thorlab)), and a single-photon detector (ID Quantique, ID-100

SMF-20), operating in standalone mode with an active quenching circuit.

FIG. 1: (Color online) (a) Experimental setup. GEN - arbitrary waveform generator, VCSEL - vertical-cavity surface-emitting laser, VOA - variable optical attenuator, SPD - avalanche single photon photodetector, OSC - oscilloscope, PC - personal computer. (b) Afterpulse detection scheme (timing diagram) τ_0 laser pulse repetition period. t_1, t_2 - times of appearance of first- and second-order afterpulses, respectively.

A series of SPDs were investigated, which had a dark count rate of 10-30 Hz, a dead time of 45-50 ns, and a photon detection probability of 0.03-0.05 at 850 nm wavelength. Laser pulses with a duration of 5 ns and a frequency of 200 kHz with variable amplitude were applied to the detector. Registration of the single-photon detector responses was carried out using a USB oscilloscope with a sampling rate of 500 MHz. The time of afterpulse appearance after the registration of the laser pulse action was measured.

The effective number of photons incident on the detector was estimated as follows. It is known that the probability of detector triggering P , depending on the average number of photons ν per pulse, is determined as $P = 1 - e^{-\eta\nu}$ [22], where η is quantum efficiency. Hereafter, we use the quantity μ defined as $\mu = \eta\nu$, which represents the average number of photons per pulse absorbed by the detector. In this case, the number of photons μ can be determined as $\mu = -\ln(1 - P)$. For large number of photons, the quantity $1 - P$ becomes extremely small, which makes measuring

such quantities very difficult or even impossible. To avoid this problem we perform a series of measurements in regime of a strong attenuation with a precisely controlled variable optical attenuator to determine the parameter μ_0 which corresponds to a number of photons in the absence of attenuation. The relationship between μ and μ_0 is determined by the following expression:

$$\mu = \mu_0 \cdot 10^{\frac{-K}{10}}, \quad (1)$$

where K is the attenuation coefficient in decibels. The probability of a photocount depending on the attenuation will then be:

$$P = 1 - e^{-\mu_0 \cdot 10^{\frac{-K}{10}}} \quad (2)$$

Expressing the triggering probability as a function of attenuation yields the following relation:

$$\lg(-\ln(1 - P(K))) = \lg \mu_0 - \frac{K}{10} \quad (3)$$

Designating $y = \lg(-\ln(1 - P))$, $a = -\frac{1}{10}$, $b = \lg \mu_0$, $x = K$, expression (3) is written as $y = ax + b$. The parameters b and μ_0 were determined from this linear dependence in the regime of strong attenuation, when the probability of detection was less than unity. Then, the parameter μ_0 and the attenuation value K were used for extrapolation to estimate the behavior for a large number of incident photons.

Figure 1 (b) shows the scheme for processing temporal signals to find photocounts corresponding to afterpulses. The recorded sequence of output pulses was divided into temporal fragments with a duration equal to the period of the optical pulse repetition. In each fragment, the number of afterpulses was counted, as well as their inter-pulse intervals.

The afterpulse probability was defined as the ratio of the number of afterpulses to the number of laser pulses. For first-order afterpulses, this is the ratio of the number of primary afterpulses to the total number of laser pulses, $P_1 = N_1/N$. For secondary pulses, this is the ratio of the number of these pulses to the total number of laser pulses, $P_2 = N_2/N$. A similar definition was used

for higher-order afterpulses. It should be noted that at intensities $\mu < 10$, the probability of detector triggering is not strictly equal to 1. When calculating afterpulse probabilities, this was taken into account by additionally dividing the obtained values by the detector triggering probability. It should also be noted that this definition of secondary afterpulses is rather conditional, as it does not account for the fact that under strong pulsed illumination, several avalanches may form simultaneously in the detector after the radiation pulse [23], which may lead to the appearance of several primary afterpulses at different times. The verification of this division into primary and secondary afterpulses will be performed below based on data analysis. The inter-pulse intervals were found as follows: in each fragment, the positions of the pulses from the detector were read, and the inter-pulse temporal intervals were found by the difference in their positions on the time axis. The first temporal interval relates to the first-order afterpulse, the second to the second, and so on.

3. Results and discussion

Figures 2(a) and 2(b) present the results of measurements of the probability of first-order (P_1) and second-order (P_2) afterpulse occurrence as a function of the number of photons (μ) absorbed by the active area of the single-photon detector.

The probability of afterpulse occurrence increases with the number of photons, with the most significant rise observed when the value exceeds approximately 100 photons. This rise in dependency at high levels of optical excitation can be explained by the increased concentration of charge carriers in the deep impurity levels of the photodiode's semiconductor structure. When a large number of photons ($\mu > 100$) are absorbed, many electron-hole pairs are simultaneously generated in the active area of the detector, which likely leads to the development of several independent avalanche processes. As a result, a large portion of carriers is captured by deep im-

FIG. 2: (Color online) (a) Dependence of the probability of occurrence of the first-order afterpulse P_1 and (b) the second-order P_2 on the average number of photons μ absorbed by the detector. The samples are denoted by numbers (1-4).

purity levels. The subsequent release of these carriers causes a repeated avalanche, which manifests as a greater number of afterpulses, thereby explaining the observed rise in afterpulse probability with increasing laser excitation intensity. 3(b)). Figure 3 presents the dependencies of the second- and third-order afterpulse probabilities (P_2 and P_3 , respectively) on the first-order probability (P_1). The dependency of probabilities P_2 and P_3 on probability P_1 can be approximated by a power function $y = \alpha x^m$. This is confirmed by the fact that the data are well approximated by a linear dependency in a double logarithmic scale. Results of the approximation by the power model showed a pronounced linear dependency in the double logarithmic scale of the probability of second- and third-order afterpulses on the first-order afterpulse probability (Figure 3(a) and Figure

Assuming that the probability of a higher-order afterpulse depends on the first-order afterpulse probability as $P_n = P_1^n$, the total number of registered pulses N should be equal to:

$$N = N_0(P_0 + P_1 + P_1^2 + P_1^3 + \dots + P_1^n + P_d), \quad (4)$$

where P_d is the dark count probability, and P_0 is the pulse detection probability. According to this model, in which the probabilities of higher-

Table 1: Linear approximation of the $P_2(P_1)$ dependence for 4 different detectors

No.	m	α
1	1.091	0.0352
2	1.171	0.0323
3	1.236	0.0936
4	1.135	0.0572

Table 2: Linear approximation of the $P_3(P_1)$ dependence for 4 different detectors

No.	m	α
1	1.124	0.0011
2	1.228	$7.123 \cdot 10^{-4}$
3	1.331	0.0063
4	1.186	0.0027

order afterpulses are generated by the afterpulse of the next lower order, the coefficient m should be equal to the order of the afterpulse; however, such behavior is not observed experimentally.

Significant deviations of this coefficient are observed from 2 in the case of second-order afterpulses (Table 1) and from 3 in the case of third-order afterpulses (Table 2).

These significant deviations may indicate that the observed afterpulses, based on the pre-

FIG. 3: (Color online) (a) Dependence of the probability of a second-order afterpulse P_2 and (b) a third-order afterpulse P_3 on the probability of occurrence of a first-order afterpulse. Detector samples are designated by numbers (1-4)

FIG. 4: (Color online) The probability density of the first-order afterpulse ρ over time t for several laser excitation levels corresponding to the specified number of photons absorbed by the detector. The plots (a-d) corresponds to different detectors. The legend indicates the effective photon numbers of the laser excitation.

viously proposed measurement scheme, are not purely higher-order afterpulses, but are a mixture

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FIG. 5: (Color online) The probability density function of first-order afterpulses ρ for 4 samples (a-d) as a function of the time t of the afterpulse occurrence and the average number of photons μ absorbed by the detector.

of primary afterpulses and corresponding higher-order afterpulses. This is likely related to the multiplicity of avalanches formed under high levels of APD illumination in single-photon measurement mode.

The probability density distribution of afterpulses over time was also found to be highly dependent on the illumination level, as shown in Figures 4 and 5. The form of the distribution varies significantly depending on the average number of absorbed photons. This change is characterized by a nonlinear redistribution of the probability density towards shorter times as the photon number increases. For most of the detectors studied, this was observed as a distinct shift

in the probability density from the 2–5 μ s range towards smaller times, with the probability density peak shifting towards the sub-microsecond domain, approaching intervals on the order of 30 ns at the highest illumination levels (see Fig. 5). While this effect was present in all four detectors, the specific form of the distributions differed between them, a variation likely related to differences in their internal semiconductor structures.

4. Conclusions

This work investigated the afterpulse statistics of single-photon detectors based on silicon

avalanche photodiodes (ID-100 SMF-20 from ID Quantique) under conditions of strong pulsed illumination. When a large number of photons ($\mu \approx 100$ and above) hit the active area of the detector, a significant change in afterpulse statistics occurs. Starting from values of the average number of photons $\mu \approx 100$, the probability of afterpulse occurrence significantly increases, potentially reaching values of 0.4 in some de-

tectors at higher excitation levels. Simultaneously, the probability density undergoes a substantial change, specifically, a redistribution towards smaller times (on the order of 30 ns). The results can be directly taken into account for detector performance in measurements and applications where high levels of detector illumination may be present.

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